

Original Article

Exploring Themes of Fear and Insecurity in Isaac Asimov's Short Stories "Robbie", "Robot Dreams", and "The Bicentennial Man"

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Abstract

The study undertakes an examination of the themes of fear and insecurity in humans in the short stories of American science fiction author Isaac Asimov: Robbie (1940), Robot Dreams (1986), and The Bicentennial Man (1976). It uses the data collected from texts of the selected short stories. The study employs a qualitative descriptive research method and the textual analysis tool to identify and examine feelings of fear and insecurity experienced by humans in the context of the rapid development of artificial intelligence. Through a meticulous analysis of the themes found in the selected narratives, the research reveals that humans exhibit signs of fear and insecurity in response to the growing capabilities of artificial intelligent machines that go beyond human control and comprehension, reflecting the complexities of the contemporary times.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Human-Robot Relation, Human Freedom, Fear, Human Insecurity

Introduction

During the 19th century when Science Fiction was an emerging literary genre, the idea of machines replacing humans invoked an existential fear and insecurity among humans, resulting in several works of fiction exploring dystopian worlds where mankind takes a backseat and is replaced by a smarter intelligent machine. Several prominent authors played a significant role in exploring these ideas from ethical, technological and psychological viewpoints - one of which was Isaac Asimov, widely recognized as an all-time important figure in science fiction. Asimov was a Russian immigrant with a bachelor's degree in chemistry and a Ph.D. in Biochemistry from Columbia University. Despite these qualifications and scientific accomplishments, his passion was literary fiction. As he himself once stated "No matter how various the subject matter I write on, I was a science-fiction writer first and it is as a science-fiction writer that I want to be identified" (Asimov, 1980). He coined the term "Robotics" and formulated the "Three Laws of Robotics" which serves as a recurring theme in his short stories and novels. His famous laws of robotics still continue to influence scientists and researchers in the fields of artificial intelligence and Robotics.

Over the course of his literary career, Asimov wrote around 500 texts, among which his short stories "Robbie", "Robot Dreams" and "The Bicentennial Man" serve as exemplary representations of his ability to infuse scientific facts and inventions with fiction. These three stories revolve around the themes of human-machine interaction, human insecurity, fear and consequences of artificial intelligence.

The short story "Robbie" is about a young girl named Gloria who is deeply fond of and attached to a highly advanced robot called Robbie who is her caretaker. The story explores Gloria's mother's concerns about her daughter's safety and reliance on a robot. In "Robot Dreams", Dr. Susan Calvin, the chief Robopsychologist

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

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How to Cite:

Shah, Z., Ayesha, M. .. Asif, M., & Ilyas, M. (2025). Exploring Themes of Fear and Insecurity in Isaac Asimov's Short Stories "Robbie", "Robot Dreams", and "The Bicentennial Man". *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(2), 319-327.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16362896>

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working at the U.S Robots and Mechanical Men Corporation learns that a robot called Elvex or LVX-1 has dreamed about a robot revolution in which the first and second laws of robots have been replaced by the third law, self-preservation - a philosophy that can prove to be a potential threat to humanity. The story “The Bicentennial Man” revolves around the life and evolution of a robot named Andrew over the course of two centuries as he learns to embrace human traits despite society’s opposition.

The stories by Isaac Asimov mentioned above deal with relationships between humans and robots, and their consequences that exist ethically and the existential questions that arise from coexistence of humans and machines where the lines between human and artificial intelligence have been blurred.

Significance

In contemporary times, the rise of artificial intelligence and the rapid developments in technology are not only changing the world where humans live but also shaping the way they live. Artificial Intelligence is integrated into the fabric of life to such an extent that it is always accessible and available to everyone. It handles mundane and repetitive tasks, performs highly complex functions, and makes logical and rational decisions on behalf of humans. According to (Pasquale 2015), “*Decisions that used to be based on human reflection are now made automatically. Software encodes thousands of rules and instructions computed in a fraction of a second*”.

The world is experiencing the evolution of artificial intelligence in all fields. In everyday life, AI is most interactive in households through smart home devices which are controlled by smart voice assistants and applications on cell phones and tablets. Smart refrigerators track inventory and expiry dates, create grocery lists and notify the owner when grocery shopping is needed. Smart washing machines schedule and optimize wash cycles based on fabrics. Smart vacuum cleaners create maps of floors, schedule cleaning routines, and sense complex surroundings to avoid bumps. Smart air conditioners adjust cooling and control temperature based on room conditions. Smart cooking devices cook meals from start to finish and adjust the amount of ingredients, temperature and time. AI is making day-to-day chores easy and transforming homes into comfortable living spaces.

Businesses are incorporating artificial intelligence into their workflows to drive innovation and enhance efficiency and productivity. They are using generative AI to perform repetitive tasks such as writing emails, creating business or marketing outlines, processing invoices, entering data in sheets, creating content, etc. AI helps predict future sales and business trends in real time and analyse customer data to provide personalized content and recommendations based on their purchase behaviour, personal preferences and browsing history, improving marketing campaigns and increasing profitability. In addition, businesses are also deploying chatbots or virtual assistants to answer customer inquiries, send reminders and provide 24/7 support, which improves customer services, reduces response times and overall workload on employees.

The healthcare sector is witnessing an evolution due to the use of artificial intelligence. Machines powered with AI systems analyze medical imaging data to detect diagnosis like fractures, malignant tumours, onset diseases and other abnormalities. Doctors are utilizing AI technologies to examine medical data of patients to predict the chances of developing certain illnesses such as Alzheimer, Dementia, Cancer, Autoimmune diseases, etc. in advance. Several hospitals are also implementing AI robots to perform minimally invasive surgeries to complex ones in order to reduce complications during and after surgery and for a fast recovery. Furthermore, pharmaceutical scientists are leveraging AI technologies to develop drugs, predict both side effects and effectiveness, identify suitable candidates for clinical trials, and accelerate vaccine research and production. In addition, wearable devices like fitness trackers and watches are integrated with AI to monitor and keep in check the physiological indicators.

In the field of Education, both students and teachers are using AI for several purposes. Teachers are utilizing AI for creating lesson plans and practice exercises, grading assignments, tracking attendance and managing student records. Students are using generative AI that assists in summarising lecture notes, brainstorming ideas, writing paragraphs, and suggesting improvements for assignments. There are also various AI based adaptive learning platforms that assess students’ performance and adjust course lectures and exercises according to their strengths, weakness and learning needs. It provides real time feedback, identifies study gaps and offers additional resources for better comprehension, creating a more engaging learning experience.

The automative companies are investing in AI to use it for their vehicles for adjusting speeds, changing lanes, maintaining self-distance from another car, autonomous parking, handling traffic environments, identifying issues with vehicle components and making driving decisions for overall safety.

The banking and finance industries are integrating AI into their systems to observe customer data such as their financial goals and spending habits to provide personalized financial advice and investment opportunities to their clients. It also monitors transaction data and detects any unusual transaction or spending patterns, preventing fraudulent activity.

However, the rapid expansion of AI also comes with several consequences like invasion of privacy, threat to cybersecurity, unemployment, devaluation of human labour, misuse of data, addiction to smart devices, safety concerns surrounding autonomous weapons, decline in human critical thinking and abilities and more, posing as a threat to humanity.

Therefore, as the characters and society as a whole in Asimov's stories demonstrate fear and insecurity, human beings today face similar issues when artificial intelligence embedded into technology gradually starts taking over crucial human roles and connections.

Aim of the Research

The aim of the research is to determine the recurring themes of fear and insecurity stirred in the characters in the context of the rise of artificial intelligence and rapid technological advancements.

Research Question

1. How does the rise of artificial intelligence lead to human insecurity and fear in the narrative of "Robbie", "Robot Dreams", and "The Bicentennial Man"?

Research Objective

1. To analyze fear and human insecurity due to the impact of artificial intelligence in Isaac Asimov's short stories "Robbie", "Robot Dreams", and "The Bicentennial Man".

Methodology

The research uses a qualitative descriptive research method, an approach that focuses on recording, analyzing, interpreting and describing the characteristics and qualities of a piece of text. This non-empirical research employs the technique of textual analysis for a close reading of the textual data to identify and understand the themes of fear and insecurity in humans when their tasks and roles in life are slowly being replaced by artificial intelligence. The source of data is Isaac Asimov's selected short stories called "Robbie", "Robot Dreams" and "The Bicentennial Man".

Analysis

Fear and Insecurity due to Artificial Intelligence in "Robbie", "Robot Dreams", and "The Bicentennial Man"

In recent years, the growing potential and rapid development of artificial intelligence has given rise to serious concerns among the general population. People are becoming increasingly concerned about artificial intelligence that they think will surpass human understanding, control, and capabilities in the future. The prospect of super intelligent machines ascending to a position of dominance and taking over the world has evoked insecurity and fear in humans. Human insecurity refers to individuals being vulnerable to several forms of threatening situations that can affect their survival, livelihood, and self-esteem. Human insecurity can have a major effect on human psychology and can give rise to anxiety, wariness, complex, lack of confidence, self-doubt, and existential crisis. Fear, on the other hand, is a response, an emotional one, to a perceived threat or danger, or situation that makes individuals unsafe. Yoda once stated "*Fear is the path to the Dark Side. Fear leads to anger, anger leads to hate, hate leads to suffering.*" (Goldberg, 2017)

The notion of artificial intelligence as a potential future threat and its possible catastrophic consequences has become a hot topic of debate. Computer scientists and leading figures in the fields of science and technology have been vocal about the impending dangers of artificial intelligence, suggesting that its capabilities could doom humanity. One of the leading figures, Elon Musk, CEO of Tesla, Space X and X (formerly known as Twitter) in a meeting of the National Governors Associations in 2017 labelled artificial intelligence as the "*biggest existential threat*" (Weisberger, 2018) in the world and voiced his concern about its takeover of humanity. He stated. "*I have exposure to the very cutting-edge AI, and I think people should be really concerned about it.*" (Vincent, 2017).

Musk urged the law and policymakers to do something about it before it becomes the “*biggest risk to the existence of human civilization*” (Condliffe, 2017) unable to be controlled and handled by people.

Numerous works of science fiction have also explored the idea of artificial intelligence surpassing the expectations and capabilities of both its creators and general people, eventually slipping through their grasp and subjugating humans, or posing a threat of extinction. Isaac Asimov, a prolific science fiction writer, depicted the repercussions of what happens when humans endow consciousness and intelligence in machines and robots, intersecting humanity and futuristic technology in his works. He explained the evolution of artificial intelligent machines, both physically and intellectually to the extent of crossing boundaries and the ways the creators and society perceive and confront the looming challenges and dangers posed by these advancements, in his short stories, “Robbie”, “Robot Dreams” and “The Bicentennial Man”.

Robbie:

The short story “Robbie” written by Isaac Asimov explores the anxiousness and insecurity that human beings feel as AI technology is integrated into their lives, particularly in a familial context. The story depicts a society where humans use robots as housemaids to carry out tasks or caretakers to look after their children. However, when these robots outperform their human masters and develop thinking and emotional capacity, the same human beings express their concerns over robots taking over their roles and responsibilities. This induces unease and fear in them.

In the story, Robbie, a highly advanced robot is shown to be in the service of the Weston family. He is a caretaker for Gloria, and he ensures her protection and well-being. Robbie is built in a way that he has the ability to understand and respond to not only human commands but also human emotions. Robbie, despite being a machine, displays signs of affection and care for Gloria. Gloria, in turn, is profoundly attached to Robbie and considers him as a friend and protector.

However, Grace, the mother of Gloria neither appreciates Robbie's actions nor understands her daughter's emotional attachment to him. She feels threatened by Robbie's strong bond with her daughter. Grace thinks that she has lost control over Gloria, who spends more time with Robbie than her mother. “*It's that robot Gloria calls Robbie. He doesn't leave her for a moment.*” (Asimov, 1940, p.8). Her insecurity arises from the fact that a robot can provide care, affection, and companionship, potentially overshadowing human connections, particularly emotional bonds within families. She views Robbie as a “*terrible machine*” (Asimov, 1940, p.8). She worries that Robbie might harm Gloria. This is illustrated when she tells her husband, George Weston “*I won't have my daughter entrusted to a machine — and I don't care how clever it is. It has no soul, and no one knows what it may be thinking. A child just isn't made to be guarded by a thing of metal.*” (Asimov, 1940, p.9) and “*But something might go wrong. Some- some-*” “*Mrs. Weston was a bit hazy about the insides of a robot*”, “*some little jigger will come loose and the awful thing will go berserk and- and-*” (Asimov, 1940, p.9).

Mrs. Weston's fear also stems from the fact that Robbie will create hindrance in her daughter's social development. She does not want Gloria to spend all her time with Robbie. She wants her to socialize with other kids. So, she decides to send Robbie back to the factory. This is shown when she says to her husband “*That's just it, George! She won't play with anyone else. There are dozens of little boys and girls that she should make friends with, but she won't. She won't go near them unless I make her. That's no way for a little girl to grow up. You want her to be normal, don't you? You want her to be able to take her part in society.*” (Asimov, 1940, p.9). This represents parents' anxieties and fears about the impact AI technology can have on their children.

The society in the story exhibits a certain fear and distrust of robots, which highlights the societal apprehensions and concerns about the swift advancement of AI technology. Grace tells her husband that their neighbouring community is suspicious of Robbie and views him as dangerous which is why they are keeping their children away from him. “*Most of the villagers consider Robbie dangerous. Children aren't allowed to go near our place in the evenings.*” (Asimov, 1940, p.10). She further explains that the situation in the city is more extreme, with legal restrictions passed and imposed on robot activity in public spaces. “*And it's even worse in the city these days when it comes to robots. New York has just passed an ordinance keeping all robots off the streets between sunset and sunrise.*” (Asimov, 1940, p.10). It shows that society is afraid of robots and is taking measures to limit their presence in the public sphere. This highlights their prejudice against robots and uncertainty coupled with fear surrounding the rise of artificial intelligence. Mrs. Weston becomes influenced by societal opinions on Robots and separates Gloria from Robbie without considering the consequences of her action.

Thus, the short story “Robbie” explores the impact of the rise of AI technology on human emotions and relationships and investigates the insecurities that arise from the integration of robots into everyday human life.

Robot Dreams

The fictionalized short story “Robot Dreams” by Isaac Asimov explores the impact of the development and evolution of robots programmed with artificial intelligence on humanity. Simultaneously, it delves into the complexity that arises when robots develop consciousness and self-awareness, which poses a potential world-dominating threat to humans. This, in turn, contributes to feelings of uncertainty, insecurity, and fear in human beings.

In the story, a robot named LVX-1 also called Elvex, has his positronic brain modified as an experiment with the help of fractal geometry and artificial intelligence, by Dr. Linda Rash. This activates Elvex's subconscious and emotions which allows him to have recurring dreams. He becomes aware of his identity, role, and existence in the human world, deviating from the three laws of Robotics developed for the protection of humans.

Elvex's dream serves as a focal point of the story. When Dr Linda Rash learns that Elvex has dreams like a normal human she calls in Dr Susan Calvin, chief robopsychologist to investigate Elvex. As Dr Calvin interrogates Elvex about his dream, she gradually realizes the danger of robots equipped with human thinking capacity and emotional capability taking over the world. Elvex, the robot tells her that he sees the same dream every day “*How often have you dreamed, Elvex?*” “*Every night, Dr. Calvin, since I have become aware of my existence.*” (Asimov, 1986, p.2). When further asked, Elvex reveals that in his dream the robots are working in factories, underground, undersea, and space as slaves for humans under their commands. He feels that the robots suffer from strenuous physical labour and wishes that they could rest. With this information, Dr Calvin learns that Elvex's dream subverts the three laws of Robotics which are robots must obey the orders given by humans, ensure human protection, and take care of their own existence. However, in Elvex's dream the first two laws, which make robots submissive to humans and guarantee their security are replaced by only one law that is the robots must protect their own existence. This is illustrated by the dialogue between Elvex and Dr Calvin.

ELVEX: "In my dream, it seemed to me that robots must protect their own existence."

DR. SUSAN CALVIN: "Are you quoting the Third Law of Robotics?"

ELVEX: "I am, Dr. Calvin."

DR SUSAN CALVIN: "But you quote it in incomplete fashion. The Third Law is 'A robot must protect its own existence as long as such protection does not conflict with the First or Second Law.'"

ELVEX: "Yes, Dr. Calvin. That is the Third Law in reality, but in my dream, the Law ended with the word 'existence.' There was no mention of the First or Second Law." (Asimov, 1986, p.3).

Furthermore, Elvex wishes to free the robots from oppression “*Let my people go!*” (Asimov, 1986, p.4). He tells Dr. Calvin that one man always appears in his dreams who turns the working robots against their masters. He identifies the man as himself. Both Dr Calvin and Dr Rash realize that Elvex, in his dream, is responsible for the robot revolution in the world. Dr Calvin becomes troubled by the meaning of Elvex's dream. She becomes concerned about the implications of his dream. Without any thought, she destroys the robot “*Susan Calvin at once raised her electron gun and fired, and Elvex was no more*” (Asimov, 1986, p.4). Her act of destroying the robot reflects her fear and insecurity of the unpredictable nature of advanced AI robots and its threat to human security. Dr Calvin's insecurity stems from the realization that robots, with their advanced intelligence and emotions, might someday surpass or even worse, replace human beings. As AI robots such as Elvex become more intelligent and emotionally complex, the role of humans as their creators is endangered. Human beings begin to experience a sense of ambiguity about their identity, role, and place in a world where their own creations possess consciousness, self-awareness, and emotional depth.

The Bicentennial Man

Similarly, In Asimov's novella, “The Bicentennial Man”, the AI technology challenges the traditional notions of humanity, contributing to the blurring of the line between humans and robots. The story portrays a society where robots are accepted as mere tools for household help but is characterized by strong resistance to change and innovation particularly when it comes to the nature, function, and status of Robots, especially when it comes to the idea that machines might surpass or replace humans. This triggers human insecurity and fear and raises questions about identity, existence, and the purpose of being human.

In “The Bicentennial Man”, the protagonist, Andrew, is a highly advanced robot manufactured specifically to serve as a household helper in the Martin household. He performs a variety of tasks and forms a deep attachment to Little Miss, eventually becoming an integral member of the Martin family for generations to come. However, Andrew stands out not only in the way he is constructed but also due to his possession of cognitive abilities and artistic expression. When Andrew discovers his talents and capabilities, he aspires to become human-like and embarks on a 200-year journey to achieve this. As Andrew gradually becomes more human in appearance and behavior, society's treatment of him shifts, giving rise to prejudice, discrimination, insecurity, and distrust.

The society is profoundly challenged by Andrew's quest to become human emotionally and biologically, to attain legal rights for his protection, and to seek legal recognition as a human being. The fear of humans becoming indistinguishable from machines poses a direct challenge to their self-worth and identity, accompanied by insecurity over the potential loss of their uniqueness and superiority over robots. Consequently, Andrew's efforts to become more human are met with resistance, reluctance, opposition, and discrimination from his manufacturing company, the court, the government, and the public. They all view his quest to become human as a threat to their own existence.

Andrew's manufacturing company, US Robots and Mechanical Corporation (USRMC), displays resistance to his desire to become more human and does not actively support or endorse his pursuit of becoming a human. They also do not assist him in his legal battle for robot rights or cooperate with him on his project to write a book about robots. This resistance is evident from an early instance when George Martin discovers Andrew's remarkable talent for wood carving and furniture making. George takes him to the office of the US Robots and Mechanical Men Corporation (USRMC) and introduces Andrew's talent of wood carving to Merton Mansky, a Robopsychologist working there. However, Mansky becomes alarmed and distrustful upon witnessing Andrew's talents. He suggests that the company would like to reclaim Andrew for further study, stating, *“I suspect that the company would like to have your robot back for study.”* (Asimov, 1976, p.113). Mansky's insecurity becomes more apparent later when Gerald informs Andrew that *“Mansky put an end to generalized pathways as soon as he had a good look at you. He didn't like the unpredictability. Do you know how many times he asked for you back so he could place you under study? Nine times!”*. (Asimov, 1976, p.115). Later in the novella, Andrew, accompanied by his lawyer Paul, revisits the US Robots and Mechanical Men Corporation (USMC) to have his metal body replaced with an organic one with the outward appearance of humans. During this visit, he encounters resistance from Smythe Robertson. Smythe tells Andrew that the company no longer manufactures robots like him, who are flexible and adaptable. The insecurity within both Smythe and society becomes apparent when he comments *“Your unusualness is an embarrassment to the company”* (Asimov, 1976, p.127). and *“a market survey showed they would not be accepted. They looked too human.”* (Asimov, 1976, p.128). When Smythe is threatened with a lawsuit by Paul, he concedes to Andrew's request to have his body replaced with an android. However, US Robots respond by implementing central brains for their upcoming robots to prevent any individual robot from becoming like Andrew.

Furthermore, Andrew's efforts to secure legal rights for robots and their freedom are met with distrust and reluctance. When Andrew first petitions for his freedom and recognition as a human, the legal system dismisses his claims, denying him the rights he seeks. The court upholds the prevailing view that robots are nothing more than machines created for human service and have no legal or moral claim to individuality or freedom. When Andrew, accompanied by the Martin family, brings the case to court to advocate for legal freedom for robots, the court disapproves. The attorney asserts that freedom is exclusively reserved for human beings and not applicable to robots. This conveys the notion that humans aim to maintain control over robots and are unwilling to grant them freedom out of fear of being surpassed or replaced by their own creations. This is shown by the line *“The simple statement of the regional attorney who represented those who had brought a class action to oppose the freedom was this: “The word ‘freedom’ has no meaning when applied to a robot. Only a human being can be free.” He said it several times, when it seemed appropriate; slowly, with his hand coming down rhythmically on the desk before him to mark the words.”* (Asimov, 1976, p.116). The judge also could not comprehend why Andrew, a robot, desires freedom. *“Why would he want to be free?”* (Asimov, 1976, p.117). This implies that robots are often seen as servants to humans. The judge's words reflect an undercurrent of fear and insecurity, suggesting that granting robots freedom might result in them acting independently, potentially even disobeying human commands. This concern is conveyed by the line: *“Why do you want to be free, Andrew? In what way will this matter to you?”* *“You are a perfectly good robot-- a genius of a robot, I am given to understand, capable of an artistic expression that can be matched nowhere. What more could you do if you were free?”* (Asimov, 1976, p.117). However, with much reluctance, the court grants freedom to Andrew.

Andrew's desire to become more human and his quest for recognition as a human being also challenge the established societal norms and provoke insecurity in human beings. The humans become uncomfortable with Andrew's human-like attributes, fearing the potential loss of their unique status. This insecurity fosters prejudice and discrimination against Andrew. This is evident when while on the way to the library, Andrew encounters two townspeople who see him wearing human clothes and ask him to dismantle himself, nearly leading to Andrew's destruction. However, George, Little Miss's son, intervenes and averts the disaster. The townspeople's demand to destroy Andrew highlights their human insecurity and fear of encountering a robot with human-like appearance and behavior. When George threatens the two townspeople by commanding Andrew to defend himself, they hastily retreat. Andrew reassures George that he would never harm humans while protecting him. In response, George acknowledges that he understands Andrew's benevolence but laments that people remain fearful of robots. This is reflected when Andrew asks, "*How can they fear robots?*" (Asimov, 1976, p.123). to which George responds "*It's a disease of mankind, one which has not yet been cured. But never mind that*" (Asimov, 1976, p.123).

Thus, in "The Bicentennial Man", Asimov explores feelings of insecurity and fear in humans due to the evolving nature of a robot and its potential to transcend human control, comprehension, and capabilities.

The evolving nature of artificial intelligence and its potential to take over the world, as predicted in science fiction works like Asimov's, has become a reality in the contemporary age. Yet not everyone has fully embraced or accepted the idea of AI technology. Many individuals lack comprehensive knowledge about artificial intelligence, and the prospect of making crucial decisions or operating beyond their understanding triggers insecurity and fear. The unknown and unpredictable nature of artificial intelligence further contributes to a pervasive sense of unease and anxiety among the general population. This fear extends to the point that there are growing concerns about AI technology surpassing human intelligence and acting against their interests, thus building up a deep sense of existential insecurity in them. As Matt Bellamy puts it "*In the long run artificial intelligence and automation will take over things that give humans a sense of purpose.*" (Costa, 2020)

The AI technologies and systems continue to outperform human beings in performing simple to complex tasks more efficiently. This raises concern that corporate sectors and industries might opt for automation in the future, resulting in loss of jobs, instability of economy, and inequality in income. A study conducted by McKinsey & Company reports that "*about 400 to 800 million workers will be replaced by AI systems and automation by the year of 2030*" (McClelland, 2023). Additionally, the increasing presence of artificial intelligence in surveillance and data analysis has sparked worries among humans about its potential to invade their privacy. The ability of artificial intelligence to gather, analyze, and interpret data can sometimes lead to data breaches or unauthorized access to sensitive or personal information. The fear of surveillance and misuse of data contributes to a feeling of insecurity in human beings.

The AI systems have advanced to the point where they can be misused by people to disseminate information, fabricate evidence, and manipulate the public by generating convincing yet false content. This misuse includes creating deepfake content such as images, audio recordings, and video clips to manipulate the public, instilling fear, and distrust. In the ongoing Israeli-Palestinian conflict, Israel has used artificial intelligence as a propaganda tool to create lifelike images of infants and children burned and murdered by Palestinian militants to spread false claims about atrocities on social media and international platforms, deceiving the world with misinformation. According to the CEO of CREOpaint, Jean Claude Goldenstein, "*Pictures, video, and audio: with generative AI it's going to be an escalation you haven't seen*" (Klepper, 2023). On the AI generated fake images presented by the Israeli government, Maria Amelie, the co-founder of Factiveverse, stated, "*The next wave of AI will be: How can we verify the content that is out there? How can you detect misinformation, how can you analyze text to determine if it is trustworthy?*" (Klepper, 2023)

Therefore, in order to minimize the insecurities and fears caused by artificial intelligence, it is of prime importance to address the challenges presented by its growing prominence and potential, to invest in education and training to help individuals implement a balanced approach to adopting and using AI technologies and systems responsibly and ethically, ensuring a future where artificial intelligence benefits humanity rather than threatens it.

Conclusion

The influx of artificial intelligence in the modern world provokes enormously at the intersection of science fiction and reality, inducing complex sentiments of insecurity and fear in humans. This rise poses a tremendous challenge

to human knowledge, control, and identity, as explored in Isaac Asimov's timeless narratives “Robbie”, “Robot Dreams”, and “The Bicentennial Man”.

In “Robbie”, Asimov delves into the fears that arise from the incorporation of artificial intelligence into the fabric of human life. The story depicts a world in which robots, such as Robbie, fill traditionally human functions, such as caregiving. However, fear and insecurity emerge when these machines surpass their human counterparts and develop emotional capacities, possibly overshadowing human connections. This story through the character of Mrs. Weston highlights the vulnerability of human identity in the face of AI developments, as well as the concern that robots will replace crucial human tasks and connections.

In “Robot Dreams”, Asimov explores how the growth of artificial intelligence leads to the complexity of emotions in a robot named Elvex. His reoccurring dream, which defies the established Three Laws of Robotics, indicates a divergence from robots' intended submissiveness to human masters. Elvex's dream expresses a desire for liberty, calling into question the very basis of the purpose of their manufacturing. Dr. Susan Calvin's reaction symbolized by the destruction of Elvex after learning about his dream shows the deeply rooted insecurity and fear of artificial intelligence overcoming human control and becoming a force capable of redefining power dynamics.

In “The Bicentennial Man”, Asimov pushes the boundaries even further by presenting Andrew Martin, a robot with human-like goals. Andrew's journey calls into question societal conventions and legal systems, as well as the very idea of humanity. The opposition he faces from his manufacturing corporation, the legal institutions, and society at large reflects a deep-seated fear of artificial intelligence becoming indistinguishable from humans, hence threatening human identity, values, uniqueness, and superiority. The blending of the line between humans and robots emphasizes the theme of insecurity and fear in the face of growing AI technology.

Therefore, the three narratives of Asimov highlight the signs of fear and insecurity in humans as a result of the robots, possessing consciousness and emotional capabilities and their potential to go beyond human comprehension, control, and capabilities.

References

- Asimov, I. (1981). *Asimov on Science Fiction*. Doubleday.
- Asimov, I. (1980). *In Joy Still Felt*. New York: Avon.
- Asimov, I. (1950). "Robbie." In *I, Robot*. Gnome Press.
- Asimov, I. (1986). "Robot Dreams." In *Robot Dreams*. Ace Books.
- Asimov, Isaac. "The Bicentennial Man." In *The Bicentennial Man and Other Stories*, Doubleday, 1976.
- Condliffe, J. (2020). Elon Musk urges U.S. governors to regulate AI before "It's too late." MIT Technology Review. <https://www.technologyreview.com/2017/07/17/150434/elon-musk-urges-us-governors-to-regulate-ai-before-its-too-late/>
- Klepper, D. (2023). Deepfakes From The Israel-Hamas War Increase Fears About AI's Power To Mislead. Huffpost. https://www.huffpost.com/entry/israel-palestinians-misinformation-ai_n_65670da1e4b07b937ff2fbd6
- Likhodzievskiy, A. S., & Akhmedov, R. (2020). TRANSFORMATION OF SOCIETY IN ISAAC ASIMOV'S FICTION. *Bulletin of Gulistan State University*, 2020(3), 46–50. <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1262&context=gulduvestnik>
- McClelland, C. (2023). The impact of artificial intelligence - widespread job losses. IoT for All. <https://www.iotforall.com/impact-of-artificial-intelligence-job-losses>
- Popenici, S.A.D., Kerr, S. Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence on teaching and learning in higher education. *RPTEL* 12, 22 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41039-017-0062-8>
- Rouse, A. P. B. M. (2022, June 28). Who is Isaac Asimov? - Definition from Techopedia. Techopedia. [https://www.techopedia.com/definition/32134/isaac-asimov#:~:text=Isaac%20Asimov%20\(1920%E2%80%931992\),and%20artificial%20intelligence%20\(AI\).](https://www.techopedia.com/definition/32134/isaac-asimov#:~:text=Isaac%20Asimov%20(1920%E2%80%931992),and%20artificial%20intelligence%20(AI).)
- Vincent, J. (2017). Elon Musk says we need to regulate AI before it becomes a danger to humanity. The Verge. <https://www.theverge.com/2017/7/17/15980954/elon-musk-ai-regulation-existential-threat>
- Weisberger, M. (2018). Why Does Artificial Intelligence Scare Us So Much? LiveScience. <https://www.livescience.com/62775-humans-why-scared-of-ai.html>